

Integration of Graphene-based Materials with Bioreceptors for Enhanced Clinical Point-of-Care and Environmental Monitoring Devices

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Our research aims to exploit the exceptional properties of graphene-based nanomaterials and bioreceptors to develop improved clinical Point-of-Care and environmental monitoring devices. Our approach centres on the fabrication of nanostructured three-electrode electrochemical cells using an environmentally friendly, low-cost, one-step printing/stamping technique. This technology utilises an infrared laser to enable the simultaneous and precise fabrication of highly exfoliated reduced graphene oxide (rGO), which is decorated in situ with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) by instantaneous laser-induced co-reduction of graphene oxide (GO) and gold cations (Au³⁺), which can subsequently be transferred onto flexible supports such as PET or nitrocellulose to form the SPEs [1]. The functionalisation of the working electrode surface with DNA-based probes, aptamers, antibodies [2] or nanobodies using different chemical approaches enables the specific capture and detection of target nucleic acids, proteins or small molecules, respectively. The incorporation of AuNPs on the rGO surface enhances the electrochemical performance of the electrodes by creating multiple active sites, increasing sensitivity for biosensor applications, while the bio-recognition elements enable high specificity. Upon binding events between the immobilised bioreceptors and the target analytes, discernible changes in the electrochemical signal are observed, enabling rapid and sensitive detection of biomarkers or environmental pollutants. The combination of DNA nanotechnology, nanomaterial-based sensors and electrochemical techniques offers a promising avenue for point-of-care detection that can range from environmental monitoring to health diagnostics.

References

[1] Annalisa Scroccarello, Ruslan Álvarez-Diduk, Flavio Della Pelle, Cecilia de Carvalho Castro e Silva, Andrea Idili, Claudio Parolo, Dario Compagnone, Arben Merkoçi. *ACS Sensors*, 8, 598 (2023).

[2] Danilo Echeverri, Enric Calucho, Jose Marrugo-Ramírez, Ruslán Álvarez-Diduk, Jahir Orozco, Arben Merkoçi, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 252, 116142, 2024.

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